

Revitalizing Workforce Wellbeing: Harnessing the Power of Reiki in the Corporate World

Çalışan Sağlığını İş Yerinde Canlandırmak: Kurumsal Dünyada Reiki'nin Gücünden Yararlanmak

Ramazan TOPAL¹ | Emine Betül KAPLAN²

¹ Dr., Alfred, New York(Alfred University, Collage of Business), Alfred, USA

ORCID: 0000-0002-7808-7535

Mail: topal@alfred.edu

² Student, Akdeniz Universty, Antalya/Türkiye

ORCID: 0009-0001-7960-4194

Mail: ebetulkaplan@gmail.com

Corresponding Author:
Ramazan TOPAL

Ay/ Yıl: Aralık/ 2023
Cilt: I
Sayı: I

Citation:

Topal, R., & Kaplan, E. B. (2023). Revitalizing workforce wellbeing: Harnessing the power of reiki in the corporate world. *KİÜ Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 1(1), 16-24.

Abstract

Abstracts: In today's age, where the welfare of employees profoundly influences the prosperity of businesses, it is absolutely essential to delve into holistic self-care approaches that embrace the diverse facets of human well-being. In the early 20th century, Japanese priest Mikao Usui developed Reiki, a simple yet highly powerful energy-centered technique, as an energy healing method. It spread to the West through Usui's students and is now widely practiced worldwide in various fields for healing, energy cleansing, stress relief, and overcoming depression and anxiety. Reiki has the potential to revolutionize the field of employment by emphasizing not only physical and mental health but also a crucial aspect of energetic well-being. This document aims to present the notion of seamlessly integrating Reiki practices within the corporate landscape as a means to elevate employee well-being, enhance productivity, and bolster job satisfaction. Within this framework, a model proposal is set forth, delineating the strategies for incorporating Reiki-centered self-care initiatives into various businesses. This proposal also spotlights the prospective advantages and obstacles associated with this novel approach. In our contemporary era, where the success of a business is intricately tied to the well-being of its workforce, there is a compelling need to explore all-encompassing self-care strategies that encompass the multifaceted dimensions of human health. Reiki, a straightforward yet potent energy-focused practice, holds the potential to revolutionize the world of work by addressing not only physical and mental health but also the vital realm of energetic well-being. This paper introduces the concept of integrating Reiki into the corporate sphere as a means of enhancing employee health, elevating productivity, and fostering job satisfaction. A proposed model lays out the framework for implementing Reiki-based self-care programs within businesses, shedding light on the potential benefits and challenges that may arise.

Key Words: Reiki, Healing, Workplace Well-being Application.

Öz

Özet: Çalışanların refahının işletmelerin refahını derinden etkilediği günümüzde, insan refahının çeşitli yönlerini kucaklayan bütünsel öz bakım yaklaşımlarını araştırmak kesinlikle çok önemlidir. 20. yüzyılın başlarında Japon rahip Mikao Usui tarafından geliştirilen, basit ancak son derece güçlü bir enerji merkezli teknik Reiki bir enerji şifa yöntemidir. Usui'nin öğrencileri aracılığıyla Batı'ya yayıldı ve bugün dünya çapında hemen pek çok ülkede, farklı alanlarda şifalanma, enerji temizlenmesi, stresten kurtulma, depresyon ve anksiyeteden arınma metodu olarak uygulanmaktadır. Reiki sadece fiziksel ve zihinsel sağlığa değil, aynı zamanda enerjik zindeliğin önemli yönüne de dikkat çekerek istihdam alanında devrim yaratma kapasitesine sahiptir. Bu belge, çalışanların refahını yükseltmek, üretkenliği artırmak ve iş memnuniyetini desteklemek için Reiki uygulamalarının şirket ortamına sorunsuz bir şekilde entegre edilmesi fikrini sunmayı amaçlamaktadır. Bu çerçevede, Reiki merkezli öz bakım girişimlerinin çeşitli işletmelere dahil edilmesine yönelik stratejileri tanımlayan bir model önerisi ortaya konmaktadır. Bu öneri aynı zamanda bu yeni yaklaşımla ilgili olası avantaj ve engellere de dikkat çekmektedir. Bir işletmenin başarısının, işgücünün refahına sıkı sıkıya bağlı olduğu çağımızda, insan sağlığının çok yönlü boyutlarını kapsayan, her şeyi kapsayan öz bakım stratejilerini keşfetmeye zorlayıcı bir ihtiyaç vardır. Basit ancak güçlü bir enerji odaklı uygulama olan Reiki, yalnızca fiziksel ve zihinsel sağlığı değil, aynı zamanda enerjik esenliğin hayatı alanını da ele alarak iş dünyasında devrim yaratma potansiyeline sahiptir. Bu makale, çalışan sağlığını iyileştirme, üretkenliği artırma ve iş memnuniyetini teşvik etme aracı olarak Reiki'yi kurumsal alana entegre etme kavramını tanıtmaktadır. Önerilen bir model, işletmelerde Reiki temelli öz bakım programlarının uygulanmasına yönelik çerçeveyi ortaya koymakta ve ortaya çıkabilecek potansiyel fayda ve zorluklara ışık tutmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Reiki, Şifalanma, İşyerinde Sağlık Pratiği.

Introduction

At the core of Reiki is the concept of life force energy, known as "ki" in Japanese or "qi" in Chinese. This is the vital force that flows within and around us, supporting the functions of the body, mind and emotions. When this energy flow becomes imbalanced or blocked, it can manifest as physical discomfort, emotional distress and mental turbulence. Reiki practitioners believe that by channeling and directing this life force energy through gentle tapping or non-tapping techniques, the body's innate healing mechanisms can be activated and lead to profound shifts in well-being.

In an era when the fast-paced corporate environment demands peak performance and relentless dedication, employee wellbeing often takes a back seat to the pursuit of bottom-line results. However, this traditional view of business success is changing as a more comprehensive understanding of employee wellbeing emerges. No longer can businesses ignore the complex interplay of physical health, mental resilience, emotional balance and the often overlooked energetic vitality of the workforce.

Historical Origins and Philosophical Foundations

Reiki has its origins in Mikao Usui in Japan in the early 20th century. Derived from the Japanese words "rei" (universal) and "ki" (life force energy), Reiki summarizes the belief in the existence of an omnipresent life force that flows through all living things. This life force, often likened to the concept of "qi" or "prana" in various Eastern traditions, is believed to be the source of vitality that maintains physical, emotional and mental balance. At the core of Reiki practice is the concept that the practitioner acts as a channel to channel this life force energy. The recipient, whether human, animal or even plant, is believed to absorb this energy, triggering a healing response. Reiki treatments often involve gently touching or even placing hands without touching certain areas of the body, allowing the energy to flow and initiate a sense of balance and well-being. While empirical evidence of Reiki's effectiveness is a subject of ongoing research, anecdotal reports and some clinical studies suggest a range of potential benefits (Mackay, N., Hansen, S., & McFarlane, O. 2004). These include stress reduction, pain management, improved sleep, enhanced immune response, and increased overall relaxation (Crawford et al., 2006). The non-invasive nature of Reiki makes it an attractive option, especially for individuals seeking alternative or complementary interventions in conjunction with conventional medical treatments. Scientific investigation of the effects of Reiki is still evolving, and studies are often limited by methodological challenges and the complexities inherent in measuring energy-based interventions. Some researchers claim that the observed benefits can be attributed to the relaxation response triggered by the calming environment and personal attention. However, recent studies using advanced imaging techniques suggest that Reiki may induce changes in brain activity and autonomic nervous system functioning, warranting further investigation (Dyer et al., 2023).

Integration into Modern Health Services

Despite the ongoing controversy surrounding the mechanisms of Reiki, Reiki is increasingly finding a place in modern healthcare settings. Recognizing the potential synergy between energy-based interventions and established medical practices, hospitals, clinics, and wellness centers have begun to offer Reiki alongside traditional medical treatments (Marvaldi et al., 2021). The integration of Reiki into patient care emphasizes the shifting paradigm towards a more holistic approach to healing, recognizing the interconnectedness of mind, body and spirit (Ferraz et al., 2017). Reiki's origins in Japanese culture give it spiritual and philosophical dimensions. As Reiki spreads across cultures and contexts, practitioners must navigate the fine line between honoring its traditional roots and adapting it to fit different worldviews. Furthermore, the lack of standardized training and certification has led to different levels of competence among practitioners, raising ethical questions about ensuring competence and providing authentic healing experiences (Doğan, 2018).

Reiki: An Energetic Way to Heal Stress, Anxiety and Depression

In a world where stress, anxiety and depression have become common problems, the search for holistic and alternative approaches to healing is increasing. Among these, Reiki, an ancient practice based on the belief in energy healing, has attracted attention for its potential to alleviate not only physical ailments but also emotional burdens that weigh down the human spirit (Thrane & Cohen 2014). By focusing on the energetic dimensions of well-being, Reiki offers a unique way to reduce stress, manage anxiety and alleviate the weight of depression.

Reducing Stress through Energy Alignment

Often regarded as a contemporary epidemic, stress exacts a toll on both our physical and emotional well-being (Lee et al., 2008). The relentless demands of daily life have a tendency to disrupt the natural flow of energy within the body, culminating in tension, restlessness, and an overwhelming sense of unease. In response to this pervasive issue, Reiki sessions emerge as a therapeutic intervention aimed at reinstating harmony within the body's energy centers, commonly known as chakras (Bandealy et al., 2021).

As the practitioner addresses and releases energy blockages during a Reiki session, recipients frequently report an exquisite sensation of deep relaxation—a veritable balm for the nervous system. This process, grounded in the reorganization of energy, offers a holistic and innate approach to finding solace amidst life's myriad challenges (Vancampfort et al., 2021). By tackling stress at its source through the restoration of energy balance, Reiki provides a natural pathway to achieving tranquility.

Moreover, when considering anxiety disorders marked by excessive worry and fear, Reiki's proficiency in inducing a profound state of relaxation emerges as a valuable asset in anxiety management. A comprehensive study conducted by Crawford et al. (2016) underscores this, revealing that participants subjected to Reiki sessions reported a noteworthy reduction in anxiety levels compared to their counterparts in the control group (Crawford et al., 2016). This research not only aligns with the experiential benefits reported by many but also contributes to the growing body of evidence supporting Reiki's efficacy in alleviating stress-related conditions, thereby solidifying its position as a holistic approach to well-being.

Reducing Anxiety and Nurturing Emotional Balance

Persistent anxiety, marked by an ongoing state of worry and heightened unease, can be overwhelming (Cavanna et al., 2023). Numerous studies have delved into the impact of Reiki on the autonomic nervous system, revealing its potential to guide the body into a state of rest and relaxation (Lantheaume et al., 2020). This shift is pivotal in anxiety management, countering the fight-or-flight response that often amplifies anxious sensations (Stafford et al., 2015). Through the energy-focused techniques and soothing touch inherent in Reiki, individuals frequently express a release of tension and an overwhelming sense of tranquility.

The serene ambiance cultivated during Reiki sessions provides individuals with a sanctuary to pacify their restless minds, fostering emotional equilibrium and a heightened sense of control over thoughts and feelings (Orsak et al., 2015). Anxiety disorders, characterized by excessive worry and fear, can significantly impact daily life. Leveraging its capacity to induce a profound state of relaxation, Reiki emerges as a potential aid for individuals grappling with anxiety. In a study conducted by Crawford et al. (2016), participants subjected to Reiki sessions reported a noteworthy reduction in anxiety levels compared to their counterparts in the control group (Vitale, 2007). This underscores the promising role that Reiki might play in alleviating the burden of anxiety, offering a holistic approach to emotional well-being.

Alleviating Depression with Energetic Rebalancing

Depression, a intricate and multi-layered condition, casts a substantial shadow over an individual's quality of life. The holistic impact of Reiki transcends the confines of the physical realm, extending into the intricate landscape of emotional and mental healing. By directly addressing emotional blockages and disrupting stagnant energy patterns, Reiki emerges as a catalyst for releasing repressed emotions that often contribute to the pervasive feelings of sadness and hopelessness (Siegel et al., 2016).

The experience of receiving Reiki is frequently described as profoundly nurturing, fostering an environment where individuals can navigate and process their emotions within the cocoon of a safe and supportive space. This therapeutic process unfolds gradually, contributing to the lifting of emotional burdens, ushering in a renewed sense of emotional buoyancy, and notably reducing the intensity of depressive symptoms over time.

Depression, being a complex mental health condition influenced by a spectrum of biological, psychological, and environmental factors, necessitates a comprehensive approach to treatment. While Reiki is not a substitute for medical interventions, emerging research suggests its potential as a complementary therapy. Studies, such as the one conducted by Shore in 2004, have hinted at Reiki's capacity to contribute to mood enhancement and overall emotional well-being, thereby offering a supplementary avenue in the holistic prevention of depressive symptoms. Integrating Reiki into a comprehensive mental health care strategy underscores its potential as a holistic and supportive element in the journey towards emotional healing.

Model Proposal

Reiki Based Employee Health Program

A Reiki-based employee wellness program is of great importance to companies in the 21st century because of its potential to address the changing needs and challenges of the modern workplace. Reiki, a holistic healing practice originating from Japan, has become increasingly important as it focuses on channeling energy to promote physical, emotional and mental well-being. For the reasons we have outlined below, companies should go beyond the traditional health package for their employees and consider practices that are truly beneficial to their employees, help them overcome the challenges they face inside and outside the organization, and help them focus and make effective decisions. We can express the importance of workplace Reiki practice as follows:

- **Stress Reduction:** Stress is a common problem in the fast-paced corporate world. Reiki helps employees manage stress by providing relaxation, reducing anxiety and improving mental clarity. A more relaxed workforce leads to increased productivity and reduced burnout (**Thrane & Cohen 2014**).

- **Mental Health Support:** In the 21st century, there is a growing emphasis on mental health in the workplace. Reiki will complement traditional mental health programs by providing employees with tools to manage their emotions, alleviate symptoms of depression or anxiety, and develop a positive mindset (Aghabati et al., 2010).

- **Remote Work Challenges:** With the rise of remote working, employees face isolation and blurred work-life boundaries. Reiki sessions can be conducted virtually, offering employees a sense of connection, relief from the stresses associated with remote work, and a private space to recharge their energy.

- **Holistic Wellbeing:** Modern workers seek holistic wellbeing beyond physical health. Reiki encompasses the mind-body-spirit connection, addresses emotional and spiritual needs as well as physical health, and aligns with 21st century holistic well-being trends (Hauptmann et al., 2023).
- **Employee Retention and Engagement:** Companies that prioritize employee well-being are more likely to attract and retain top talent. A Reiki-based program demonstrates a commitment to the overall health of employees, which can increase engagement and loyalty (Agdal et al., 2011).

- **Cost-Effective Health:** Reiki is a cost-effective health option compared to traditional medical interventions. Companies can provide regular Reiki sessions to their employees without a significant financial burden, making it an accessible wellness solution.
- **Diversity and Inclusivity:** Reiki is inclusive and can be practiced by people of all backgrounds and beliefs. It respects different perspectives on wellbeing, promoting an inclusive workplace culture.

A Reiki-based employee wellness program is aligned with the evolving needs of the 21st century workforce. It offers a holistic approach to wellbeing, addresses mental health issues, supports remote working dynamics and contributes to employee retention and engagement. By embracing Reiki as part of their wellness initiatives, companies can create healthier, happier and more productive workplaces in the modern age.

Now below are the headings of the recommended model and how it can be briefly used within the organization.

Reiki Training Programs: Organize regular Reiki training programs at the workplace. An expert Reiki instructor teaches employees the basics of Reiki and energy management techniques. These trainings help develop stress coping skills.

Energy Focused Executive Trainings: Organize energy-focused trainings for managers. These trainings enable managers to maintain their own energy balance and understand the energy levels of their team members. Managers can apply energy management techniques to improve team performance.

Energy Focused Team Building Activities: Make team building activities energy focused. Whether it's nature walks, meditation sessions, or group energy balancing exercises, employees can build a closer relationship with each other and share positive energy.

Energy Break Times: Take energy breaks at specific times during the day. These breaks give employees the opportunity to do short meditations, breathing exercises or light physical activities. This way, employees can re-energize and regain their focus.

Reiki Salons: Create dedicated Reiki lounges at work. These spaces are decorated in soothing colors and have a calming ambiance to help employees reduce stress. Employees can come to these areas during their short breaks and receive Reiki sessions. Each session can last 15-20 minutes and employees have the opportunity to renew their energy.

Combination of yoga and Reiki: Combine yoga and Reiki sessions at work. Yoga sessions improve body flexibility, while Reiki sessions help balance energy. This combination supports both the physical and energetic health of employees.

Discussion

The integration of Reiki into the corporate world as a comprehensive employee wellness initiative is bringing a transformative shift in the way businesses approach workforce wellbeing. As organizations recognize the undeniable link between employee health, job satisfaction and overall performance, the Reiki-based model offers a holistic approach that aligns with the evolving understanding of wellbeing. Through this approach, companies have the opportunity to significantly improve employee well-being on many levels. Research has consistently demonstrated the stress-reducing and anxiety-relieving effects of Reiki (Kryak & Vitale 2011). Incorporating regular Reiki sessions into the workday can create a space for employees to recalibrate their energy, manage stress and develop a greater sense of emotional balance. This in turn can lead to improved mental clarity, increased resilience, and an overall sense of satisfaction with the work environment.

In addition, adopting Reiki as part of the organizational culture sends a message of genuine care for the comprehensive well-being of employees. The presence of Reiki sessions during working hours sends a clear signal that the organization values its employees as whole individuals and recognizes that their energy, emotions and mental states contribute to their effectiveness (Lipinski & Van De Velde 2020). This could inspire a shift in attitudes towards self-care and encourage workers to prioritize their health and

well-being as a core aspect of their professional journey, rather than as an afterthought. The positive impact of this approach to Reiki on employee engagement and productivity cannot be overstated. As employees experience the benefits of reduced stress and increased mental clarity through Reiki sessions, they are likely to become more engaged in their role (Hailey et al., 2022). A workforce that feels supported and valued is more motivated to do their best, resulting in increased creativity, improved problem solving and greater commitment to achieving organizational goals (Natale, 2010).

On the other hand, feelings of burnout and high turnover rates are significant challenges in many workplaces today (Ngô, 2013). Implementing a Reiki-based employee wellness program can serve as a proactive measure to combat burnout and improve employee retention. The stress-relieving effects of Reiki can help prevent burnout by providing employees with a practical tool to manage their stress levels (Cramer et al., 2017). Furthermore, organizations that prioritize employees' holistic wellbeing are more likely to retain their talent because employees feel a strong sense of loyalty towards an employer who genuinely cares about their overall health (Notte et al., 2016).

Challenges and Considerations

While the benefits of integrating Reiki into the corporate environment are compelling, some challenges should be considered. Skepticism may arise among employees who are unfamiliar with energy-based practices. To overcome this, extensive educational efforts are required to familiarize employees with the principles and benefits of Reiki. Also, it can be difficult to find time for Reiki sessions within a demanding work schedule. However, demonstrating the positive impact of short Reiki breaks on productivity and overall job satisfaction may alleviate this concern.

Conclusion

In an age where the boundaries between work and private life are blurring and the human experience is recognized as multifaceted, the incorporation of Reiki into the corporate world marks a transformative shift in the way businesses prioritize employee wellbeing. A Reiki-based employee wellness program is not only a tactical response to modern challenges, but also a profound statement of the organization's commitment to holistic care and sustainable success.

Businesses that embrace Reiki embark on a journey to create a workplace culture that recognizes employees as dynamic beings with complex layers of physical, emotional, mental and energetic needs. This recognition aligns with the changing expectations of the workforce - individuals who seek not only material fulfillment, but also an environment that nurtures their growth, supports their challenges and strengthens their sense of purpose.

The Reiki-based model doesn't just offer a new program; it represents a cultural evolution. It represents a shift towards workplaces that prioritize not only productivity and innovation, but also emotional resilience, mental clarity and energetic vitality. Through the regular practice of Reiki, employees can experience stress reduction, emotional balance and a renewed connection with their inner selves, so they can navigate the complexity of their roles with grace and purpose.

Furthermore, the adaptation of Reiki into the corporate fabric has the potential to ripple outward, shaping the organization's reputation in the wider business environment. Companies that invest in the holistic wellbeing of their employees become beacons of positive change and influence their colleagues to reconsider their own approach to employee care. This shift not only transforms the work environment, but also contributes to a societal paradigm where employee wellbeing is one of the core principles of business ethics. However, as companies embrace Reiki and the broader concept of holistic wellbeing, they take on a role that goes beyond the traditional scope of profit generation. They become agents of an ecosystem where individuals are empowered to thrive in all areas of their lives, spreading their vitality and positive energy to coworkers, customers and communities. With its foundations in energy and interconnectedness, a Reiki-based employee wellness program becomes a conduit for fostering authentic,

sustainable success that transcends financial metrics and touches the heart of human potential. The innovative business approach in Turkey, establishments that prioritize human health, and business structures valuing complementary and/or alternative healthcare practices unfortunately do not seem to receive the necessary attention and importance for Reiki and similar health applications within businesses in Turkey, despite the profile of individuals who embrace complementary and alternative health approaches. This study has been initiated to draw attention to this issue.

The public opinion survey conducted by Harris Interactive in the USA reveals the effect of stress on employees. In the survey, it was found that 42 per cent of employees made more mistakes at work due to stress, and 34 per cent had arguments with their friends. Other studies also support this research. For example, according to the US Bureau of Labour Statistics, employees take about 20 days off a year due to stress or a stress-related condition. According to the Princeton Screening Survey, 75 per cent of employees believe that workers are under more stress than the previous generation. As such, world-famous companies and brands such as AOL, Apple, Deutsche Bank, Google, HP, IBM, Nike, Microsoft, Reebok, Yahoo, Shell have made meditation, which is a part of Asian culture, a necessity of daily life. Many giant companies start the day with meditation or offer meditation seminars to their employees. A similar situation is observed in Turkey. However, it is not seen that companies take any systematic steps in this regard. In addition to the title above, which we offer as a model suggestion, companies can also include the following health practices on their agenda (Ülker, 2018).

Here are a few examples of some health practices that are similar to Reiki:

Qigong: This is a practice of Chinese origin that focuses on balancing and improving the flow of "chi" or "qi", which is considered the life energy in the body. The main purpose of Qigong is to support physical and mental health, reduce stress and awaken the energy in the body.

Tai Chi: Tai Chi is a Chinese exercise system consisting of slow and fluid movements. Tai Chi is used to increase balance, improve body awareness, increase flexibility and keep energy in balance.

Prana Therapy: This practice originates from India and aims to balance "prana", known as life energy. Prana therapy involves channelling energy using your hands or body and is used to promote physical and emotional healing.

Crystal Therapy: Crystal therapy aims to balance energy using special crystal stones. Each crystal stone is believed to have different energies, so appropriate crystals can have positive effects on body energy.

Reconnective Healing: This practice promotes access to universal energy, which is thought to be able to help the body and mind heal itself. Reconnective healing practitioners seek to connect to universal energy rather than directing energy using their hands.

Jin Shin Jyutsu: This Japanese-derived practice aims to balance the flow of energy using the energy meridians in the body. It tries to rebalance the person's energy meridians using simple touches and holds.

There are many energy-based or energy-orientated health practices similar to Reiki. These practices aim to balance one's energy, promote healing or provide physical and emotional relief.

REFERENCES

- Agdal, R., von B Hjelmberg, J., & Johannessen, H. (2011). Energy healing for cancer: a critical review. *Forschende Komplementarmedizin* (2006), 18(3), 146-154. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000329316>
- Aghabati, N., Mohammadi, E., & Pour Esmail, Z. (2010). The effect of therapeutic touch on pain and fatigue of cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy. *Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine : eCAM*, 7(3), 375-381. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ecam/nen006>
- Bandealy, S. S., Sheth, N. C., Matuella, S. K., Chaikind, J. R., Oliva, I. A., Philip, S. R., Jones, P. M., & Hoge, E. A. (2021). Mind-Body Interventions for Anxiety Disorders: A Review of the Evidence Base for Mental Health Practitioners. *Focus (American Psychiatric Publishing)*, 19(2), 173-183. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.focus.20200042>.
- Crawford, S. E., Leaver, V. W., & Mahoney, S. D. (2006). Using Reiki to decrease memory and behavior problems in mild cognitive impairment and mild Alzheimer's disease. *Journal of alternative and complementary medicine (New York, N.Y.)*, 12(9), 911-913. <https://doi.org/10.1089/acm.2006.12.911>.

- Crawford, S. E., Leaver, V. W., Mahoney, S. D., & Sollars, D. L. (2016). A pilot study to investigate the effects of reiki on pain and anxiety in the elderly. *Journal of Alternative and Complementary Medicine*, 22(9), 681–684.
- Cramer, H., Lauche, R., Klose, P., Lange, S., Langhorst, J., & Dobos, G. J. (2017). Yoga for improving health-related quality of life, mental health and cancer-related symptoms in women diagnosed with breast cancer. *The Cochrane database of systematic reviews*, 1(1), CD010802. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD010802.pub2>.
- Cavanna, A. E., Purpura, G., Riva, A., Nacinovich, R., & Seri, S. (2023). The Western origins of mindfulness therapy in ancient Rome. *Neurological sciences : official journal of the Italian Neurological Society and of the Italian Society of Clinical Neurophysiology*, 44(6), 1861–1869. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10072-023-06651-w>.
- Demir Doğan M. (2018). The effect of reiki on pain: A meta-analysis. *Complementary therapies in clinical practice*, 31, 384–387. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctcp.2018.02.020>.
- Dyer, N. L., Baldwin, A. L., Pharo, R., & Gray, F. (2023). Evaluation of a distance reiki program for frontline healthcare workers' health-related quality of life during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Global advances in integrative medicine and health*, 12, 27536130231187368. <https://doi.org/10.1177/27536130231187368>
- Ferraz, G. A. R., Rodrigues, M. R. K., Lima, S. A. M., Lima, M. A. F., Maia, G. L., Pilan, C. A., Neto, Omodei, M. S., Molina, A. C., El Dib, R., & Rudge, M. V. C. (2017). Is reiki or prayer effective in relieving pain during hospitalization for cesarean? A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Sao Paulo medical journal = Revista paulista de medicina*, 135(2), 123–132. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1516-3180.2016.0267031116>.
- Hailey, K., Fortin, J., Pratt, P., Forbes, P. W., & McCabe, M. (2022). Feasibility and Effect of Reiki on the Physiology and Self-perceived Stress of Nurses in a Large US Hospital. *Holistic nursing practice*, 36(2), 105–111. <https://doi.org/10.1097/HNP.0000000000000475>.
- Hauptmann, M., Kutschan, S., Hübner, J., & Dörfner, J. (2023). Bioenergy therapies as a complementary treatment: a systematic review to evaluate the efficacy of bioenergy therapies in relieving treatment toxicities in patients with cancer. *Journal of cancer research and clinical oncology*, 149(6), 2607–2619. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00432-022-04362-x>
- Kryak, E., & Vitale, A. (2011). Reiki and its journey into a hospital setting. *Holistic nursing practice*, 25(5), 238–245. <https://doi.org/10.1097/HNP.0b013e31822a02ad>.
- Lantheaume, S., Montagne, M., & Shankland, R. (2020). Intervention centrée sur les ressources pour réduire les troubles anxieux et dépressifs chez les patients atteints de cancer : Une étude pilote [Intervention focused on resources to reduce anxiety and depression disorders in cancer patients: A pilot study]. *L'Encephale*, 46(1), 13–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.encep.2019.07.005>.
- Lee, M. S., Pittler, M. H., & Ernst, E. (2008). Effects of reiki in clinical practice: a systematic review of randomised clinical trials. *International journal of clinical practice*, 62(6), 947–954. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1742-1241.2008.01729.x>.
- Lipinski, K., & Van De Velde, J. (2020). Reiki, nursing, and health care. *The Nursing clinics of North America*, 55(4), 505–519. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cnur.2020.06.018>.
- Mackay, N., Hansen, S., & McFarlane, O. (2004). Autonomic nervous system changes during Reiki treatment: a preliminary study. *Journal of alternative and complementary medicine (New York, N.Y.)*, 10(6), 1077–1081. <https://doi.org/10.1089/acm.2004.10.1077>.
- Marvaldi, M., Mallet, J., Dubertret, C., Moro, M. R., & Guessoum, S. B. (2021). Anxiety, depression, trauma-related, and sleep disorders among healthcare workers during the COVID-19 pandemic: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Neuroscience and biobehavioral reviews*, 126, 252–264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2021.03.024>.
- Natale G. W. (2010). Reconnecting to nursing through Reiki. *Creative nursing*, 16(4), 171–176. <https://doi.org/10.1891/1078-4535.16.4.171>.
- Notte, B. B., Fazzini, C., & Mooney, R. A. (2016). Reiki's effect on patients with total knee arthroplasty: A pilot study. *Nursing*, 46(2), 17–23. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.NURSE.0000476246.16717.65>.
- Ngô T. L. (2013). Les thérapies basées sur l'acceptation et la pleine conscience [Acceptance and mindfulness-based cognitive-behavioral therapies]. *Sante mentale au Quebec*, 38(2), 35–63. <https://doi.org/10.7202/1023989ar>.
- Orsak, G., Stevens, A. M., Brufsky, A., Kajumba, M., & Dougall, A. L. (2015). The effects of Reiki therapy and companionship on quality of life, mood, and symptom distress during chemotherapy. *Journal of evidence-based complementary & alternative medicine*, 20(1), 20–27. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2156587214556313>.
- Siegel, P., da Motta, P. M., da Silva, L. G., Stephan, C., Lima, C. S., & de Barros, N. F. (2016). Reiki for Cancer Patients Undergoing Chemotherapy in a Brazilian Hospital: A Pilot Study. *Holistic nursing practice*, 30(3), 174–182. <https://doi.org/10.1097/HNP.0000000000000146>.
- Shore, A. G. (2004). Long-term effects of energetic healing on symptoms of psychological depression and self-perceived stress. *Alternative Therapies in Health and Medicine*, 10(3), 42–48.
- Stafford, L., Thomas, N., Foley, E., Judd, F., Gibson, P., Komiti, A., Couper, J., & Kiroopoulos, L. (2015). Comparison of the acceptability and benefits of two mindfulness-based interventions in women with breast or gynecologic cancer: a pilot study. *Supportive care in cancer : official journal of the Multinational Association of Supportive Care in Cancer*, 23(4), 1063–1071. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00520-014-2442-6>.
- Thrane, S., & Cohen, S. M. (2014). Effect of Reiki therapy on pain and anxiety in adults: an in-depth literature review of randomized trials with effect size calculations. *Pain management nursing : official journal of the American Society of Pain Management Nurses*, 15(4), 897–908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmn.2013.07.008>.
- Vanhaecht, K., Seys, D., Bruyneel, L., Cox, B., Kaesemans, G., Cloet, M., Van Den Broeck, K., Cools, O., De Witte, A., Lowet, K., Hellings, J., Bilsen, J., Lemmens, G., & Claes, S. (2021). COVID-19 is having a destructive impact on health-care workers'

- mental well-being. *International journal for quality in health care : journal of the International Society for Quality in Health Care*, 33(1), mzaa158. <https://doi.org/10.1093/intqhc/mzaa158>.
- Vancampfort, D., Stubbs, B., Van Damme, T., Smith, L., Hallgren, M., Schuch, F., Deenik, J., Rosenbaum, S., Ashdown-Franks, G., Mugisha, J., & Firth, J. (2021). The efficacy of meditation-based mind-body interventions for mental disorders: A meta-review of 17 meta-analyses of randomized controlled trials. *Journal of psychiatric research*, 134, 181–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2020.12.048>.
- Ulker, B.(2018, January 31). İş dünyasında meditasyon modası. *Dünya*. [İş dünyasında meditasyon modası - Dünya Gazetesi \(dunya.com\)](https://www.dunya.com).
- Vitale, A. (2007). Reiki: A complementary therapy for life. *Holistic Nursing Practice*, 21(4), 167–171.